

Workplace Interior Design and Employee Performance

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Corporations can no longer afford to waste their workforce's potential in today's competitive business climate. There are a number of essential aspects at work that have a big impact on an employee's motivation and performance. The study's major goal is to figure out how employees' performance is related to their job. The investigation's outcomes demonstrate that the design of a workplace has a significant influence on staff productivity. It's more about building workspaces that inspire employees and increase performance than it is about integrating marketing content and amplifying business culture. Employee motivation should be a primary consideration in workplace design. This is accomplished through balancing aesthetics with functionality, health, and performance in the workplace's interior design.

Keywords: INTERIOR DESIGN, WORKPLACE, ARCHITECTURE, EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCES

Introduction

Before you can begin implementing a new office interior, you must first gain a better understanding of office interior design and how it affects the perceived quality of your company's products and services. More than fluffing up couches and placing trinkets is involved in interior design. It's the art of using color, lighting, materials, and technology to create interior décor and furnishing design concepts for commercial and residential properties. Businesses no longer continue to spend their workforce's

capabilities in modern business. There are a number of crucial aspects in a worker's workplace that have a big influence on the intention and performance.

Interior Design

Interior design is both a highly specialized field, and it entails the development of design concepts based on the emotive, integrating physical, social, and psychological drivers of a client utilizing sophisticated computer-aided design technologies and strategic planning consulting services. Though no two customers or spaces are alike, each design concept is unique to the person who will be using it (Ato, 2021).

According to the literature, effective office design boosts employee productivity; this theory is being investigated in this research. This is a new topic in Ghana, and few studies in the field of interior design have been conducted. As a result, the goal of this article is to investigate the impact of office interior design aspects

on performance management in Ghana's private sector firms. The research is confined to the facility's interior design and does not include other areas of the workplace.

Objectives

The article examines workplace interior design at several private sector companies in Ghana, as well as studies conducted to better understand employee performance as a result of their physical work environment. The goals of the research study are as follows:

- To comprehend the interaction between employees and their working environment.
- The purpose of this study is to look into how the interior design of an office influences job performance.
- To see if the layout of the office does have an impact on employee.

Literature Review

A generally held belief is that a better work environment leads to better results. The majority of the time, the workplace is created with the nature of the job and the people who will be working there in mind. Employees, technology, and the corporation's goals all have an impact on productivity at the corporate level. It's often influenced by office design as well as its impact on employee quality and development.

Interior Design

The term interior design refers to a specific type of home/office furnishing, but the art of designing and cultivating rooms, homes, offices and even entire buildings has a long and rich history that frequently incorporates art, architecture, and even philosophy. Interior design became a widely used term in the mid-1800s. (Stan Carey, 2002).

Interior design is the art and science of enhancing the interior of a building to achieve a healthier and more aesthetically pleasing environment for the people using the space. An interior designer is someone who plans, researches, coordinates, and manages such enhancement projects. Interior design is a multifaceted profession that includes conceptual development, space planning, site inspections, programming, and research, communicating with the stakeholders of a project, construction management, and execution of the design. Each person receives, perceives, in response to differences in past observation, religion, physical status, age, level of education, gender, socioeconomic class and expectations are factors which influence the needs of the occupants with role of motivation. From the early shelters to the present structure, the mental and psychological impact of architectural frames on human beings has been considered. Because human activity is carried out in specified spaces, the physical space needs to be built based on the behavioral features of people.

Historical Background of Interior Design

The term "interior architecture" refers to all of the fixed and movable ornamental elements that make up the interior of every human dwelling. It's important to note that much of what is now considered sculpture and displayed in galleries and museums was once used to decorate interiors. (Gura, 2013). Paintings were often

arranged by scale and subject from a painter who often dabbled in other art styles, such as furniture design and decoration. Goldsmiths who did a number of ornamental metalworks were often employed as stone or bronze sculptors. Interiors, including furniture, pottery, porcelain, silver, rugs, and tapestries, were designed by several architects. Paintings were frequently in the style of cabinet paintings, which were framed to be hung on a wall in a certain location, such as over a fence. Murals were painted on a variety of themes, and during the Baroque era in the 17th century, murals were often painted to act as an extension of the interior itself, giving the impression of more space.

Mirrors were used for the same reason of creating more space in a room. In most times, the intentional use of antiques as furniture was uncommon. When new decoration was undertaken to put an old interior into line with modern trends, features of the previous decorative scheme were generally confined to less important rooms in older houses. Many antiques have been saved in this way. The art market has existed from the beginning of time to include both modern and ancient pieces for the decoration of interiors, but the market for old work was typically confined to portraits by respected masters and goldsmith's work in the early days. The concept of interior design arose as part of a settled rural way of life in the past. Nomadic cultures' tents were not well suited to more permanent ways of decoration. Carpets and rugs, on the other hand, have been used by Central Asian nomads to decorate and provide warmth in tents and temporary homes, commonly in the form of floor and bed coverings. and these have become the peoples' primary forms of speech. The earliest nomadic carpet, discovered in Central Mongolia in the 5th century BC, is believed to be based on earlier carpet designs, as are geometrically patterned stone reliefs from Assyria in the 7th century BC. Hunting cultures dwelling in caves painted the walls as early as 20,000 years ago, but these were almost completely destroyed. However, these were almost definitely votive portraits rather than decoration, and there is no evidence of movable furniture. ([Britannica, 2021](#))

Materials and methods

This chapter explains the study technique as well as the theoretical underpinnings of the methods, as well as their definitions for the benefit of the readers. It began by determining the research methods. Then there was a discussion on the research plan. Finally, a brief discussion of the study's validity and reliability is included. Accordingly, the goals of this chapter are to: Explain this research approach and strategy, Introduce the research techniques that were developed in the pursuit of these research goals.

Research Design

The research technique is determined by the study objectives. The design style is focus on the current and archaic design settings, there is mostly a primary category that influence the occupant reaction. Relaxation, enthusiasm, and domination are three of them. The library research approach method was employed in this study. The next sections of this chapter will describe these topics.

Discussion

There are several elements that influence workplace interior design of an employee's performance. Shape and background, active element of the office space; light and color, focal point, space and area are all examples of design elements. Before beginning the design process, it's necessary to research the available materials, techniques, and talents. Also, attaining the space's needed purpose is crucial to producing a functional design. Finally, understanding the design's theme will help to enrich the design and give it more aspects. The designer, as much as the inhabitant, must live the tale of design. Colors, materials, forms, prices, and qualities are all influenced by the topic. (Alkrableh., 2009).

Steps of the Design Process

These steps should be followed by a designer when creating an office space following in order:

- a. The site inventory, site analysis, project program, producing the proposed program, drawings of the idea, developing the concept, and obtaining the final design are all tasks that must be completed.
- b. Determine the duties that will be performed in the area, as well as the gender and number of people that will be living there.
- c. Examining all aspects of space, as well as the organic links between masses and space (Ali A. , 2011).
- d. Investigating the effects of natural and artificial lighting (e.g., fiber glass, steel, wood, glass, gypsum, aluminum etc.). Furthermore, designers must consider the many ways in which the space's colors might be used. (Alkrableh., 2009)
- e. To acquire the finest places and functions, it's crucial to conduct analytic research of the windows and the proper distribution of furniture items. (Ali, 2011)
- f. Analyzing furniture placement in relation to the space's absorption capacity as well as the purpose.
- g. Electricity distribution and lighting pots are being given special attention. (Alkrableh., 2009)
- h. The importance of paying attention to accessories in completing the overall concept of the room cannot be overstated. As a result, it's critical to pay close attention while selecting these accessories. (Alkrableh., 2009).

Conclusion

In conclusion, as a researcher I would say there is more to it than fluffing up couches and placing trinkets in an office space. The colors, spacing, lighting, arrangement and, many more might affect the worker knowingly or unknowingly. All this should be factored into designing when the interior decoration is being done.

Satisfaction in living environments leads to good word-of-mouth and motivations for effective and fast productivity, which leads to a rise in demand for more products. As a result, factors listed above should be considered when creating a work space., willingness to offer a quotation to be utilized for institution endorsement, and perception that the institution cared about them.

Recommendation

This chapter goes into great depth regarding all of the research's problems and step by step approach in making

an employee's work space comfortable for effective productivity. It provides detailed frameworks for all aspect of the research, from interior design to satisfaction variables. This was originally included at the start of the article to provide readers with a broad knowledge of the topics. As a result, all of the information given allows the researcher to use it in subsequent phases to complete the research process, which is referred to as research methods. Factors like design, lighting, color, spacing and many more should be considered when creating an office space because it plays a major role in motivating an employee's performance in an office.

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